

Cyber Literacy as Moderator on Leadership Aptitude of School Heads and Teachers' Conscientiousness

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Abstract. The study aimed to investigate the moderating effect of cyber literacy on the interaction between the leadership aptitude of school heads and teachers' conscientiousness. In this study, the researcher selected 175 elementary school teachers in the Kiblawan South District in Davao del Sur as the respondents of the study. A stratified random sampling technique was utilized in the selection of the respondents. A non-experimental quantitative research design using a descriptive-correlational method was employed. The data collected were subjected to the following statistical tools: Mean, Partial Correlation, and Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that school heads' leadership aptitude and teachers' cyber literacy were described as extensive, while teachers' conscientiousness was rated as moderately extensive. Further, partial correlation analysis demonstrated a significant relationship between the leadership aptitude of school heads and teachers' conscientiousness when moderated by cyber literacy. Regression analysis proved that cyber literacy was an important moderator of the interaction between the leadership aptitude of school heads and teachers' conscientiousness. The Department of Education (DepEd) ensured that education policies reflect the importance of cyber literacy by incorporating technology standards and guidelines into curriculum frameworks and teacher certification requirements. The study, therefore, was conducted to further utilize findings through publication in a reputable research journal.

KEY WORDS

1. cyber literacy 2. leadership aptitude 3. conscientiousness

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1. Introduction

Addressing teachers' lack of conscientiousness requires a multifaceted approach, including professional development opportunities focused on organization, time management, and instructional best practices. School leaders also play a crucial role in providing support, feedback, and accountability to ensure that all teachers are effectively meeting their students' needs. Additionally, fostering a positive school culture that values collaboration, professionalism, and a commitment to student success can help mitigate issues related to the lack of conscientiousness among educators. On the contrary, the lack of conscientiousness among teachers can negatively impact student achievement. Students may not receive the support, guidance, and high-quality instruction they need to succeed academically. Previous research indicated that poor conscientiousness among teachers can have significant negative consequences for both

students and the overall educational environment. Tulin et al. (2018) reported that teachers who lack conscientiousness may not consistently prepare and deliver high-quality lessons. This inconsistency can result in uneven learning experiences for students, impacting their academic progress. Adding more, Cubel et al. (2017) pointed out that teachers who are not conscientious may struggle with maintaining an organized and structured classroom environment. This can lead to disruptions, wasted instructional time, and difficulty in managing student behavior. Taking things in Philippine setting, Gonzales (2022) pointed out that lack of conscientiousness resulted in teachers failing to follow through on commitments, such as grading assignments in a timely manner, providing feedback to students, or meeting with parents to discuss student progress. Not conscientious teachers may overlook their students' individual needs, such as providing appropriate accommodations for students with disabilities or offering additional support to struggling learners. Cyber literacy, as described by Hosseini and Kamal (2012), is the knowledge, skills, and competencies educators need to navigate, use, and teach about digital technologies, the internet, and information and communication technologies (ICTs) effectively, responsibly, and securely. According to Pratolo and Solikhati (2021), school heads become more proficient in navigating digital platforms and understanding technological trends, they can effectively model the importance of staying updated and utilizing digital resources for teaching and learning. This demonstration of leadership aptitude in the realm of technology can inspire teachers to adopt a similar mindset, encouraging them to embrace digital tools and integrate them into their instructional practices. Adding more, Çam and Kiyici (2017) noted that school leaders with strong cyber literacy skills are better equipped to support and guide teachers in effectively incorporating technology into their classrooms. As highlighted by Halimah and Norizah (2017), leadership aptitude of school heads plays a crucial role in improving the efficiency of a school. Strong school leaders build cohesive teams by fostering a positive and inclusive school culture. When staff members feel valued and supported, they are more likely to work together harmoniously and contribute to the school's success. According to Peñaflor (2013), leadership aptitude of school heads has a significant impact on the learning motivation of students. Effective school leadership creates an environment that inspires and encourages students to engage in their learning, take ownership of their education, and strive for academic success. Adding more, Bembo (2016) pointed out that school heads with strong leadership aptitude set a positive and enthusiastic tone for the school. When students see their leaders excited about education, they are more likely to develop a positive attitude toward learning. Previous literatures indicated that leadership aptitude of school heads plays a critical role in influencing teachers' conscientiousness. For instance, Burket (2011) that school heads who exhibit effective leadership qualities can create an environment that encourages and supports conscientious behavior among teachers, leading to improved teaching practices, enhanced student outcomes, and a positive school culture. Similarly, in the study conducted by Sağlam et al. (2017), school heads with leadership aptitude can foster a school culture that values conscientiousness and promotes a sense of responsibility among all staff members. When consistently reinforced, this culture encourages teachers to prioritize thoroughness, accountability, and ethical behavior. Likewise, Zepeda (2013) made clear that school heads with high leadership aptitude set high expectations for academic achievement and behavior. Meanwhile, Anguiano-Carrasco et al. (2015) highlighted that conscientious teachers set high standards for themselves and their students. Their commit-

ment to maintaining these standards motivates them to continuously improve their teaching methods and practices. Also, Ali et al. (2019) pointed out that conscientious teachers actively seek professional development opportunities to enhance their skills and knowledge. Their commitment to lifelong learning contributes to their effectiveness as educators. According to Bowling (2013), conscientious teachers exhibit ethical behavior and integrity, aligning their actions with their commitment to fostering positive values and citizenship traits in their students. Limited research has explored the role of cyber literacy as a moderating variable in the relationship between leadership aptitude and teachers' conscientiousness. There was a lack of studies

examining whether the level of cyber literacy among teachers influences how the leadership qualities of school heads and teachers' conscientiousness interact and impact educational processes. Thus, it was in this context that the researcher felt the need to fill in the research gap by conducting a study in the Philippine setting, particularly in the Kiblawan South District in Davao del Sur, using a quantitative approach. Specifically, the researcher used a descriptive correlational design to understand the moderating effect of cyber literacy on the interaction between the leadership aptitude of school heads and teachers' conscientiousness, which is found to be scarce.

2. Methodology

This section contains the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—In this study, the researcher utilized quantitative descriptive-correlational research techniques to gather data ideas, facts, and information related to the leadership aptitude of school heads, conscientiousness, and cyber literacy of teachers. Bryman and Bell (2015) described quantitative research as focusing on the objective measurement and analysis of numerical data to draw conclusions and make inferences about a specific population or phenomenon. This approach employs systematic and structured data collection techniques, such as surveys, experiments, or statistical analysis of existing datasets, to gather quantitative and statistically analyzed numerical data. The findings from quantitative research aim to provide a deeper understanding of patterns, relationships, and trends within the data. Meanwhile, descriptive correlational research, according to Gay, Mills, and Airasian (2019), is an approach that involves observing and measuring two or more variables without manipulating

them. It aims to describe the relationship or association between variables as they naturally occur. This approach focuses on understanding the strength and direction of the relationship between variables, often using statistical measures such as correlation coefficients. In a descriptive correlational study, researchers collect data on variables of interest and analyze them to identify patterns, trends, or associations. The goal was to better understand how the variables relate to each other in a specific population or context. This approach was particularly useful when exploring complex phenomena or when causality cannot be established due to ethical or practical limitations. The study mainly focused on determining the moderating effect of cyber literacy on the interaction between school heads' leadership aptitude and teachers' conscientiousness.

2.2. Research Respondents—The study's respondents were elementary school teachers in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur. In this study, the 175 respondents were selected

through stratified random sampling. According to Leedy and Ormrod (2018), stratified random sampling is a probabilistic sampling technique used in research to choose a representative sample from a population by dividing it into subgroups or strata based on specific characteristics. Within each stratum, a random sample was drawn, which was combined to create the final representative sample for the study. This method ensured that each subgroup was adequately represented in the sample, allowing for more accurate generalizations and inferences about the entire population. Moreover, the primary consideration of this study was to select respondents who could provide information to achieve the purpose of this study. Hence, only those permanent-regular elementary school teachers in Kiblawan South District in Davao del Sur, those who are not subjected to any administrative or criminal complaints, and those who voluntarily signed the ICF were given the survey questionnaires. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the prob-

lem based on the research questions and thus it did not consider the gender and socio-economic status of the teachers.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—The study employed questionnaires adapted from different studies and was modified to fit the context of the respondents of this study. The instrument was divided into two parts. The first part of the instrument concerned the leadership aptitude of school heads, which was conceptualized by Kadri et al. (2022). The questionnaire comprised four domains: visionary thinking, strategic planning, inspirational leadership, and community engagement. The researcher modified the questionnaire by grouping all the items in each dimension under each domain. In the manner of answering the questionnaire, the items the respondents made used the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of the supervisory competence of school heads, the researcher made use of the range of means, descriptions, and interpretations as presented below:

Range of Mean, Descriptive Level, and Interpretation for Leadership Aptitude of School Heads

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The leadership aptitude of school heads is always observed.
3.40 - 4.19	Extensive	The leadership aptitude of school heads is oftentimes observed.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The leadership aptitude of school heads is sometimes observed.
1.80 - 2.59	Less Extensive	The leadership aptitude of school heads is seldom observed.
1.00 - 1.79	Not Extensive	The leadership aptitude of school heads is never observed.

The second part of the instrument was about the conscientiousness of teachers, which was intellectualized by Shrestha and Dangol (2020) and divided into four domains: modeling ethical

behavior, creating a safe environment, promoting responsibility, and individualized support. The researcher modified the questionnaire by grouping all the items in each dimension under

each domain. In the manner of answering the questionnaire, the items the respondents made used the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of conscientiousness of teachers, the researcher made use of the range of means, descriptions, and interpretations as presented below:

Range of Mean, Descriptive Level, and Interpretation for Conscientiousness of Teachers

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The conscientiousness of teachers is always manifested.
3.40 - 4.19	Extensive	The conscientiousness of teachers is often-times manifested.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The conscientiousness of teachers is sometimes manifested.
1.80 - 2.59	Less Extensive	The conscientiousness of teachers is seldom manifested.
1.00 - 1.79	Not Extensive	The conscientiousness of teachers is never manifested.

The third part of the instrument was about the cyber literacy of teachers, which Metin (2011) had intellectualized. The Cronbach alpha coefficient for this instrument is 0.967, which was described as excellent and interpreted as reliable and consistent. In the manner of answering the questionnaire, the items the respondents made used the 5-Likert scale. As a guide in determining the extent of conscientiousness of teachers, the researcher made use of the range of means, descriptions, and interpretations as presented below:

Range of Mean, Descriptive Level, and Interpretation for Cyber Literacy of Teachers

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The cyber literacy of teachers is always evident.
3.40 - 4.19	Extensive	The cyber literacy of teachers is oftentimes evident.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The cyber literacy of teachers is sometimes evident.
1.80 - 2.59	Less Extensive	The cyber literacy of teachers is seldom evident.
1.00 - 1.79	Not Extensive	The cyber literacy of teachers is never evident.

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—

The researcher undertook the steps in conducting the study after validating the research questionnaire. Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher secured the permission to conduct the study. The researcher secured the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City, and the ethics compliance certificate from the Research Ethics Committee (REC). The endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City, and the ethics compliance certificate from the Research Ethics Committee (REC) was attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the school's division superintendent, and then to the school principals of the selected public schools in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur. Distribution and Retrieval of the Question-

naire. The researcher distributed the research instrument to the respondents after they had been approved to conduct the study. The study was conducted last January 4-5, 2024. Upon distributing the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents of the study. For the questionnaire administration, the researcher distributed the questionnaires following health protocols. The study participants were given enough testing time to finish the questionnaires. After this, the data collected were subjected to quantitative analysis. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data. After the questionnaire was retrieved, the scores of each respondent were tallied to organize the data per indicator. Then, each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was useful in characterizing the leadership aptitude, conscientiousness, and cyber literacy of school heads and teachers in Kiblawan District, Davao del Sur. It was used to supply the answer for objectives 1, 2, and 3. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was utilized to determine the significance of the relationship among the three

variables—leadership aptitude of school heads, conscientiousness, and cyber literacy of teachers in Kiblawan District, Davao del Sur. It is a statistical measure of the strength of a linear relationship between paired data. In a sample, it is usually denoted by r . Hierarchical Regression Analysis. It was applied to evaluate the moderating effect of cyber literacy on the interaction between the leadership aptitude of school heads and conscientiousness in Kiblawan District, Davao del Sur.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the study's objectives, as explained in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extents of leadership attitude of school heads, conscientiousness, and cyber literacy of teachers in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur; the significant relationship between leadership attitude of school heads and conscientiousness of teachers in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur when moderated by cyber literacy; and the moderating effect of cyber literacy on the interaction between leadership attitude of school heads and teachers' conscientiousness in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur.

The Summary of the Leadership Aptitude of School Heads in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur

Table 1 shows the summary of the leadership aptitude of school heads in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur. It shows that the overall

mean of leadership attitude of school heads is 3.50, described as extensive and interpreted as often observed. According to Cranston (2002), effective leaders empower their staff by delegating responsibilities, giving them autonomy, and trusting them to make decisions.

Table 1. Summary of Leadership Aptitude of School Heads in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Visionary Thinking	3.41	Extensive
Strategic Planning	3.57	Extensive
Inspirational Leadership	3.40	Extensive
Community Engagement	3.60	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.50	Extensive

The result indicates that the inherent or developed abilities, skills, traits, and qualities that enable them to effectively guide, manage, and inspire their school community toward achieving educational excellence and holistic growth are oftentimes observed. This supports the view of Mansor and Izham (2017) that effective school leaders have a clear vision for the school’s future and set strategic goals that align with that vision. They create a roadmap for the school’s growth and improvement, which helps guide all activities and decisions toward a common purpose. The leadership aptitude of school heads in terms of community engagement acquired the highest mean score of 3.60, which was described as extensive and interpreted as often observed by the teachers. The leadership aptitude of school heads in terms of inspirational leadership got the lowest mean score of 3.40, which was described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed by the teachers.

Adding more, results in Table 2 show that teachers’ conscientiousness in terms of creating a safe environment acquired the highest mean

ers.

The Summary of Teachers’ Conscientiousness in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur

Table 2, is the summary of teachers’ conscientiousness in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur. As shown in the table, teachers’ conscientiousness obtained an overall mean score of 3.37 with a descriptive rating of moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested by the elementary school teachers. This implies that the personality trait characterized by qualities such as organization, responsibility, attention to detail, thoroughness, and a strong sense of duty is sometimes manifested. The result is congruent to Hassan’s et al. (2018) view that conscientious teachers are diligent in their work, adhere to high standards of performance, and take their responsibilities seriously. This trait influences how teachers approach their teaching roles, interactions with students, colleagues, and the overall educational processes.

score of 3.59, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested, while teachers’ conscientiousness in terms of individual-

Table 2. Summary of Teachers’ Conscientiousness in Kiblawan South District in Davao del Sur

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Modeling Ethical Behavior	3.28	Moderately Extensive
Creating a Safe Environment	3.59	Extensive
Promoting Responsibility	3.35	Moderately Extensive
Individualized Support	3.24	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.37	Moderately Extensive

ized support acquired the lowest mean score of 3.24 described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested by the teachers. According to Rikoon et al. (2016), conscientious teachers feel a strong sense of responsibility toward their students’ education and well-being. This sense of duty fuels their commitment to providing the best learning experiences and outcomes.

Relationship Between Leadership Aptitude of School Heads and Teachers’ Conscientiousness in Kiblawan South District in Davao del Sur when Moderated by Cyber Literacy

The results of the analysis of the relationship between the leadership aptitude of school heads and teachers’ conscientiousness in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur, when moderated by cyber literacy are presented. Partial correlation analysis was utilized to determine the relationship between the variables mentioned. Table 3 shows that the leadership attitude of school

heads has a significant positive relationship with teachers’ conscientiousness when moderated by cyber literacy with a p-value of .000, which is less than the .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .902, p > 0.05$). This means that as the leadership aptitude of school heads improved, teachers’ conscientiousness also significantly improved when moderated by cyber literacy. More so, result on the table shows that leadership aptitude of school heads in terms of visionary thinking; strategic planning; inspirational leadership; and community engagement significantly correlated with teachers’ conscientiousness as evident on correlation coefficient value of 0.889, 0.774, 0.807 and 0.801, respectively. Thus, this lead to the rejection of null hypothesis of no significant relationship between leadership aptitude of school heads and teachers’ conscientiousness in Kiblawan South District in Davao del Sur when moderated by cyber literacy.

The result corroborates with Pratolo and Solikhati’s (2021) idea that school heads become more proficient in navigating digital platforms and understanding technological trends; they can effectively model the importance of staying updated and utilizing digital resources for teaching and learning. This demonstration of leadership aptitude in technology can inspire teachers to adopt a similar mindset, encouraging them to embrace digital tools and integrate them into

their instructional practices. Çam and Kiyici (2017) noted that school leaders with strong cyber literacy skills are better equipped to support and guide teachers in effectively incorporating technology into their classrooms. They can provide valuable resources, training opportunities, and guidance on best practices for integrating technology into pedagogy, which can enhance teachers’ confidence and competence in utilizing digital tools. Moderating Effect of Cyber

Table 3. Relationship Between Leadership Aptitude of School Heads and Teachers' Conscientiousness in Kiblawan South District in Davao del Sur when Moderated by Cyber Literacy

Variables	r-value	p-value	Decision
Visionary Thinking	0.889*	0.000	Reject H0
Strategic Planning	0.774*	0.000	Reject H0
Inspirational Leadership	0.807*	0.000	Reject H0
Community Engagement	0.881*	0.000	Reject H0
Overall Leadership Aptitude of School Heads	0.902*	0.000	Reject H0

*Significant @ $p > 0.05$

Legend: Perfect Correlation for $r = 1.00$; Strong Correlation for $0.7 < r < 1.00$; Moderate Correlation for $0.3 < r < 0.7$; Weak Correlation for $0.3 > r > 0.00$; No Correlation for $r = 0.00$

Literacy on the Interaction Between Leadership Aptitude of School Heads and Teachers' Conscientiousness in Kiblawan South District in Davao del Sur

The moderating effect of cyber literacy (CL) on the interaction between the leadership aptitude of school heads (LA) and teachers' conscientiousness (TC) was tested using regression analysis. Results in Table 4 show that the Beta coefficients for the Step 1 analysis of leadership aptitude of school heads (LA) and teachers' conscientiousness (TC) were $= 0.106$, S.E. $= 0.053$, $p > 0.05$; and cyber literacy (CL) and teachers' conscientiousness (TC) were $= 0.187$, S.E. $= 0.049$, $p > 0.05$. When leadership aptitude of school heads (LA) and cyber literacy (CL) of teachers were included as the only independent variables (without including an interaction term), the regression model explained 31.90 of the variance in teachers' conscientiousness (TC) ($R^2 = 0.319$, $p > .05$). Moreover, Beta coefficients for the Step 2 analysis of leadership aptitude of school heads (LA) and teachers' con-

scientiousness (TC) were $= 0.221$, S.E. $= .051$, $p > 0.05$; cyber literacy (CL) and teachers' conscientiousness (TC) were $= 0.163$, S.E. $= 0.048$, $p > 0.05$; and moderator (LA*CL) and teachers' conscientiousness (TC) were $= 0.190$, S.E. $= 0.051$, $p > 0.05$. Also, it was indicated that when an interaction between the leadership aptitude of school heads (LA) and cyber literacy (CL) was added, the percentage of variance in teachers' conscientiousness (TC) was 38.80 ($R^2 = 0.388$; $p > 0.05$) indicated the independent contribution of each variable while controlling for the influence of others to create the regression equation for each analysis, after assuring significance by examining accompanying p-values. Hence, the interaction term accounted for an additional 6.90 of variance in the dependent variable ($R^2 = 0.069$). Based on the result, the null hypothesis was rejected as cyber literacy (CL) had significantly moderated the interaction between leadership aptitude of school heads (LA) and teachers' conscientiousness (TC).

This affirmed that cyber literacy (CL) is an undeniable factor that help improve the interaction between the leadership aptitude of

school heads (LA) and teachers' conscientiousness (TC). This supports Joshi's (2018) assertion that cyber-literate school leaders can pro-

Table 4. Moderating Effect of Cyber Literacy on the Interaction Between Leadership Aptitude of School Heads and Teachers’ Conscientiousness in Kiblawan South District in Davao del Sur

Step 1		Teachers’ Consci- entious- ness (TC)	B	Beta	S.E.	p-value
Decisions						
Leadership (LA)	Aptitude	.106**	.088	.053	.000	Reject H0
Cyber Literacy (CL)		.187**	.091	.049	.003	Reject H0
R ² = 0.319		F-value = 19.224**		p-value = 0.000		
Step 2		B	Beta	S.E.	p-value	
Decisions						
Leadership (LA)	Aptitude	.221**	.088	.051	.002	Reject H0
Cyber Literacy (CL)		.163**	.095	.048	.000	Reject H0
Moderator (LA*CL)		.190**	.086	.051	.000	Reject H0
R ² = 0.388		F-value = 21.701**		p-value = 0.000		

*Significant @ p>0.05

vide valuable resources and professional development opportunities for teachers to enhance their technological skills. By offering training sessions, workshops, and access to digital tools, leaders empower teachers to develop their cyber

literacy and integrate technology in meaningful ways to support student learning. According to Eshet (2002), when school leaders demonstrate competence in cyber literacy, they inspire confidence and trust among teachers.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the conclusions and recommendations of the researcher. The discussions were supported by the literature presented in the first chapters and the conclusions were in accordance with statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study was to evaluate the moderating effect of cyber literacy on the interaction between leadership aptitude of school heads significantly influence the conscientiousness of teachers utilizing non-experimental quantitative design using descriptive-correlation technique. The re-

searcher selected the 175 elementary school teachers in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur as the respondents through stratified random sampling method. The researcher made use of modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires which was pilot tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consis-

tenacy of the items in the instrument. Leadership aptitude of school heads in Kiblawan South District in Davao del Sur got an overall mean of 3.50 with extensive descriptive rating. Also, leadership attitude of school heads in terms of visionary thinking; strategic planning; inspirational leadership; and community engagement obtained the mean scores of 3.41, 3.57, 3.40, and 3.60, respectively. Teachers' conscientiousness in Kiblawan South District in Davao del Sur got an overall mean of 3.37 with moderately extensive descriptive rating. Also, teachers' conscientiousness in terms of modelling ethical behavior; creating a safe environment; promoting responsibility; and individualized support obtained the mean scores of 3.28, 3.59, 3.35, and 3.24, respectively. Moreover, cyber literacy of teachers in Kiblawan South District in Davao del Sur got a mean rating of 3.40 described as extensive. Partial Correlation Analysis indicated that leadership aptitude of school heads has a significant positive relationship with the teachers' conscientiousness when moderated by cyber literacy with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .902, p > 0.05$). Cyber literacy of teachers was a significant moderator on the interaction between leadership aptitude of school heads and teachers' conscientiousness in Kiblawan South District in Davao del Sur. The analysis showed that when an interaction between leadership aptitude of school heads and cyber literacy was added, the percentage of variance in teachers' conscientiousness was 38.80 ($R^2 = 0.388; p > 0.05$) indicated the independent contribution of each variable while controlling for the influence of others to create the regression equation for each analysis, after assuring significance by examining accompanying p-values. Hence, the interaction term accounted for an additional 6.90 of variance in the dependent variable ($R^2 = 0.069$).

4.2. *Conclusions*—Based on the findings of this study several conclusions were generated: Leadership aptitude of school heads

in Kiblawan South District in Davao del Sur was rated as extensive. Leadership aptitude of school heads in terms of visionary thinking; strategic planning; inspirational leadership; and community engagement obtained extensive ratings. The result indicates that the inherent or developed abilities, skills, traits, and qualities that enable them to effectively guide, manage, and inspire their school community towards achieving educational excellence and holistic growth was oftentimes observed. Teachers' conscientiousness in Kiblawan South District in Davao del Sur was rated as moderately extensive. Meanwhile, teachers' conscientiousness in terms of modelling ethical behavior; promoting responsibility; and individualized support obtained moderately extensive ratings, while, conscientiousness of teachers in terms of creating a safe environment got an extensive rating. This implies that the personality trait characterized by qualities such as organization, responsibility, attention to detail, thoroughness, and a strong sense of duty was sometimes manifested. Cyber literacy of teachers in Kiblawan South District in Davao del Sur was oftentimes evident. This implies that the personality trait characterized by qualities such as organization, responsibility, attention to detail, thoroughness, and a strong sense of duty was sometimes manifested. This means that the basic digital skills like using computers and the internet but also includes the ability to critically evaluate online information, communicate effectively through digital platforms, and integrate technology seamlessly into teaching practices was oftentimes evident among teachers. There was significant positive relationship between leadership aptitude of school heads and teachers' conscientiousness in Kiblawan South District in Davao del Sur when moderated by cyber literacy. This means that cyber literacy was a significant factor that contributes to the interaction between leadership aptitude of school heads and teachers' conscientiousness in Kiblawan South District in

Davao del Sur. Cyber literacy was a significant moderator on the interaction between leadership aptitude of school heads and teachers' conscientiousness in Kiblawan South District in Davao del Sur. It is emphasized in this study that cyber literacy is an undeniable factor that intervened on the interaction between leadership aptitude of school heads and teachers' conscientiousness in Kiblawan South District in Davao del Sur. This means that cyber-literate teachers can provide valuable resources and professional development opportunities for teachers to enhance their technological skills. By offering training sessions, workshops, and access to digital tools, leaders empower teachers to develop their cyber literacy and integrate technology in meaningful ways to support student learning

4.3. Recommendations—The Department of education (DepEd) may ensure that education policies reflect the importance of cyber literacy by incorporating technology standards and guidelines into curriculum frameworks and teacher certification requirements. DepEd may also allocate resources and funding to support the design and implementation of professional development programs focused on leadership skills, conscientious teaching practices, and cyber literacy for educators at all levels. School heads may demonstrate strong leadership apti-

tude by modeling conscientious behavior, embracing technology, and actively engaging in professional development opportunities to enhance their own skills and knowledge. Adding more, school heads must allocate resources for the acquisition of technology infrastructure, software, and training materials necessary to support teachers' development of cyber literacy skills and effective integration of technology into teaching practices. Teachers may take initiative to enhance leadership skills, conscientious teaching practices, and cyber literacy through self-directed learning, participation in workshops and courses, and collaboration with colleagues. Teachers may collaborate with colleagues to exchange ideas, share experiences, and learn from each other's successes and challenges. Establish professional learning communities focused on leadership, conscientiousness, and cyber literacy to support ongoing growth and development. Future researchers may evaluate the impact of professional development programs, policy initiatives, and school-based interventions aimed at improving leadership aptitude, conscientiousness, and cyber literacy among educators. Use rigorous research methods to assess outcomes and identify areas for improvement.

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